

PERFORMANCE AND EMISSION CHARACTERISTICS OF A C.I. ENGINE FUELED WITH MUSTARD OIL AND LINSEED OIL BLENDS USING DIFFERENT SURFACTANTS

CHITRADURGA BHASKAR, AVULA HARINATH, VENNAPUSA VENKATA SIVA REDDY

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ^{1,2}, ASSOCAITE PROFESSOR ³

bhaskarcv007@gmail.com, harisreenu306@gmail.com, sivareddy.vennapusa1@gmail.com

Department of Mechanical Engineering,

Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,

N.H 44, Hampapuram, Raphadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract --When internal combustion engines run on traditional fuels, pollutants grow, endangering the environment. Conventional fuels are seeing rising demand on a daily basis. Because of this issue, other fuels are being used. Due to their low emission qualities, biodiesels are regarded as the best alternative fuels. As a result, we need to figure out how to boost the efficiency of I.C. engines while simultaneously decreasing their fuel consumption. This experiment included the transesterification of mustard oil and linseed oil to produce biodiesel. Hence, several surfactants, such as span-20, tween-20, and CTAB (cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide), are used to examine the performance and emission characteristics of a C.I. engine.

Keywords--CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide), mustard oil, linseed oil, surfactants, span-20, and tween-20.

I. INTRODUCTION

Interest in oil-based equities has risen due to the world's increasing industrialization and automation. As one of the world's fastest-growing economies, India is attracting more attention in the transport sector because to its steady economic growth. Properly speaking, this interest is equivalent to fuel utilisation. To maintain its current pace of growth, India must seek for an alternative. As far as our diesel needs are concerned, biodiesel is an upbeat option. Visit interferences and liabilities with oil's flexibility and cost have emerged as a result of this. Regardless of how much oil is estimated to cost right now, this situation over the long term might lead to a rapid scarcity of oil and its use. This points to the increased scrutiny of biodiesel, particularly more reasonable alternatives like alcohols and vegetable oils.

Biofuels are potential alternative energy sources. Much has been said about how they, as a potential alternative fuel, may be useful in lowering energy prices throughout the globe. Putting vegetable oil in a diesel engine is not a green idea. The fact is that vegetable oils were used in the early days of motors. Similar to diesel, vegetable oils have practically necessary characteristics such as a high cetane number and calorific value. Their heating capacity is commendable, and they produce very little sulphur and aromatic polycyclic chemicals in their exhaust. Because they are derived from plants, the use of vegetable oils results in a total amount of CO₂ that may be recycled.

Due to their endless supply and ease of production in adjacent zones, vegetable oils have long been a comforting alternative to diesel oil. However, since the introduction of internal combustion engines, demand for "vegetable oil" has been fierce.

In this way, mustard oil is used for food purposes in several parts of India. Mustard oil is often not recognised in the southern part of the country, even if it is edible. Figure 1(a) below, Consequently, mustard seeds are abundant and might be a viable alternative fuel source. Figure 1(b) shows that Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*) is an annual crop with a plant height of 30-100 cm and blue flowers. "Very valuable plant" is the literal translation of the plant's Latin name. The seeds are 4-to 6-centimeters long, oval-shaped, shiny, reddish-colored, flavorful, and oily. They don't smell.

The surface tension between two liquids or a solid and a liquid may be reduced by substances known as surfactants. As an emulsifier, a surfactant may be useful. To lower the surface tension between the two oils and examine their physicochemical qualities, such as firepoint, viscosity, thickness, and calorific value, this study adds surfactants such as span-20, tween-20, and CTAB (cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide). A compression ignition engine is used to test the emissions and performance properties of bio-diesel fuel that has surfactants added to it.

Fig:1(a).Mustardseeds

Fig:1(b).linseedseeds

According to SEDA ŞAHİNet.al [1], Combinations of conventional diesel fuel and linseed biodiesel were tested in a range of ratios, including B2 (98% diesel + 2% biodiesel), B5 (95% diesel + 5% biodiesel), B20 (80% diesel + 20% biodiesel), and B50 (50% diesel + 50% biodiesel). All fuels were subjected to testing of their qualities. The results showed that linseed biodiesel and fuel blends had engine performance values that were comparable to regular diesel fuel.

Finding that the clean linseed oil mix (L100) indicated poorer brake thermal efficiency, greater BSFC, higher HC, CO, and lower NO_x emissions, L. Narsing Rao et.al.[2] investigated the performance and emission characteristics of a diesel engine that was fueled with biodiesel utilising linseed oil. be that as it may, the B25 linseed-diesel mix outperformed base diesel in every metric of performance and emissions.

In a study conducted by Prof. C.S. Koli et.al. [3], the performance of a single-cylinder, four-stroke diesel engine was evaluated using a combination of diesel and two vegetable oils—mustard oil and palm oil—in proportional volumes. The BB 10 and BB 20 blends, which consist of 90% diesel, 5% mustard oil, and 10% palm oil by volume, respectively, outperformed the other blends in terms of brake thermal efficiency and brake specific fuel utilisation.

The use of Palm Kernel oil and Eucalyptus oil methyl esters as a full replacement for diesel in CI motors was investigated by K. Srinivas, Dr. B. Balu Naik, Dr. K. Kalyana Radha, and colleagues [4]. Their tests showed that a biofuel mix of 85% Palm Piece oil and 15% Eucalyptus oil exhibited Diesel-like characteristics, with a 9% increase in NO_x and a 37% reduction in smoke emissions.

R. G. Prathap One study by Dr. K. Hemachandra Reddy et.al. [5] showed that a diesel engine using a combination of rapeseed and sunflower oils outperformed the control group in terms of emissions. In order to conduct the trial study, several proportions of these oils (B05, B10, B15, B20, and B25) were mixed with diesel by volume. The results showed that the blend B20's brake thermal efficiency was 2% better at high loads than diesel's. Compared to diesel fuel, the blend's brake specific fuel consumption was somewhat lower. Compared to diesel, the CO emissions are over 28% lower. Compared to regular gasoline, the CO₂ emissions from all mixes were lower. With the exception of B20, which has a 20% reduction, almost all of the blends had greater HC emissions than diesel. Despite B20's somewhat lower NO_x emissions relative to diesel fuel, it was found that all mixes increased NO_x emissions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS OF PRODUCTION

A. Mustard oil and Linseed Oleolysis from Seeds

In India, you may find mustard fields filled with many varieties of the mustard plant, which belong to the genera Brassica and Sinapis. The mustard plant's seeds are the source of mustard oil. The mustard seeds are cleaned and checked for damage before the oil is extracted. The seeds are sun-dried until their covering changes, at which point they are transformed into a goliath limit holder extractor. Approximately 90% of the oil in mustard was removed using a mechanical smasher. the figure in question (a).

Linseed—The Linaceae family includes the flax plant, which is used to extract linseed oil. Many countries, including the United States, Canada, Argentina, and India, grow this plant. The unsaturated fat content of linseed oil, for instance, might vary typically depending on factors including the climate and components used to grow the yields, the seeds' characteristics, and the crude oil refining method. Hexane extraction is one way to get linseed oil. Image 2(b)

Fig.2(a)Mustardoil

Fig.2(b)Linseedoil

A. surfactants:

The surfactants would lower the inter-solution surface tension. Due to their incompatibility, the two fluids form a thermodynamically unstable combination. To make the fluids solid, just a little amount of surface-dynamic operators (surfactants) are required. The interfacial tension between linseed oil and mustard oil is reduced by concentrating the surfactant at the fluid contact. This causes a balancing effect by altering the free energy between the surfaces. When it comes to surfactant desire, non-ionic surfactants are preferred above cationic and anionic surfactants.

Considering a distinctive unsaturated fat (lauriccorrosive) and sugar liquid sorbitol, span20 is a biodegradable surfactant (fig. 2(c)). This sorbitan ester works wonders in creating emulsions of oil and water. Figure 2(d) is another name for Tween-20. The non-ionic surfactant polysorbate 20, also known as Scattics, Alkest TW 20, or Tween 20, is formed by ethoxylation of sorbitan prior to the expansion of lauric acid. Its relative lack of toxicity and relative consistency make it useful as an emulsifier and cleaner in a wide range of industrial, pharmaceutical, and home uses. The cationic surfactant CTAB (cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide) Fig.2(e) lowers the viscosity of the liquid, which aids combustion, and also reduces the tension between the liquids.

Fig.2(c)Span-20

Fig.2(d)Tween-20

Fig.2(e)CTAB
(cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide)

B. Trans-esterificationofmustardoilandlinseed oil:

Several parameters govern trans-esterification, including catalyst concentration, reaction temperature, humidity, free unsaturated fatty acid content, and in Biodiesel manufacturing primarily aims at selecting an appropriate and cautious transesterification measure. For this test, biodiesel was made by mixing 250 mL of methanol with 1 L of crude linseed oil. Catalysts in the business often make use of sodium and potassium hydroxides because of how easy and accessible they are. The amount of catalyst KOH used in this study was about 8.56 g. The reaction lasted for two hours, and a magnetic stirrer was used to mix the ingredients at 600 rpm. Isolating the glycerine from the biodiesel for 12 hours was the next step in the process. To remove any remaining glycerine or contaminants, the methylester that had been extracted from glycerol was rinsed with purified water. Half of the refined water at 60°C was splashed over the ester and gently shook

in this cycle. The water-and debasement-containing hazy bottom layer was removed. Next, the methyl ester was subjected to a vacuum and heated to 650C for 1 hour with the use of a rotary evaporator in order to remove any remaining methanol and water. After three hours of drying in anhydrous Na₂So₄, the methyl ester was screened through a channel articles that are subjective. It is also possible to make biodiesel by trans-esterifying mustard oil. Figures 2(f) and 2(g) below depict the process of making biodiesel from mustard oil and linseed oil.

Fig.2(f)MagneticStirrerapparatus

Fig2(g)Mustardoil+Linseedoil+glycerine

C. Characteristicsofmustardoilandlinseedoilwithdifferentsurfactants

Thepropertiesofmustardoilandlinseedoilwasassessedandcontrastedwiththe diesel.

Thepropertiesoftheblendsofbiodiesel are determined utilizing standard ASTM techniques and are noted down. The properties of various blends are appeared in the tables. Inthisinvestigation,ininitialstage Mustard oil85percentand linseed oil15percentisgivesbetter performance so for this 3 percent of Span-20, Tween-20 and CTAB surfactants are added.

TableI:PropertiesofMustardoil,Linseedoil,anddiesel

property	Mustardoil	Linseed oil	Diesel
Density(kg/m ³)	884	913	830
KinematicViscosity(Cst)	13.5	41.6	3.7
Flash point(°C)	220	236	70
CalorificValue(KJ/Kg)	39827	37831	42700
CetaneNumber	46	38	50

TableII:Propertiesofbiodieseldispersedwithdifferent surfactants

Property	M85L15	M82L15S3	M82L15T3	M82L15CTAB3
Density(kg/m ³)	888	890	895	894
KinematicViscosity(Cst)	21.13	22.27	24.89	23.85
Flash point(°C)	45	43	43	44
Calorific Value(KJ/Kg)	39745	39800	39840	39790

Where,

M85L15:Mustardoil85%+Linseedoil 15%

M82L15S3: Mustard oil 82% + Linseed oil 15% + Span-20 3%

M82L15T3:Mustardoil82%+Linseedoil15%+Tween-203%

M82L15CTAB3:Mustardoil82%+Linseedoil15%+cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide3%

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND TEST PROCEDURE

The apparatus for the experiment includes a motor, a dynamometer, a fuel tank, a manometer, and an air filter. The engine used is a water-cooled, Anil type four-stroke, single-cylinder engine. The results of the engine's self-representation sorting are detailed in Table III. Before starting the engine, make sure the fuel and lubricating oil levels are correct. Fuel may then be sucked into the engine via the opening of the three-way cock. The delta pipe is used to provide the engine with cooling water. The engine is started and allowed to prepare for 5 minutes at the evaluated speed. Put the required loads into the engine. The following data were recorded: time required to use 10cc of gasoline, engine load, manometer readings, and speed under different loads. The AVL DIGAS444 five gas analyzer was used to conduct the emission test.

Table III: Technical Specifications of engine

Make	Anil
Engine details	Single cylinder compression ignition four stroke water cooled diesel engine
Compression ratio	17.5:1
Rated power	3.7KW
Cylinder Bore and stroke	80mm and 110mm
Load	1500rpm

(a)

(b)

Fig.3(a),(b). Single cylinder compression ignition four stroke water cooled diesel engine

Fig.3(c) Exhaust gas Input

Fig.3(d) AVL-DIGAS444 fire gas analyser

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance characteristics

Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE), The below Fig.4.1(a) shows variation of brake thermal efficiency with break power for different blends mustard oil and linseed oil with different surfactants. It is clear from the graph that the efficiency for blend M82L15T3 is higher compared to other blends and is increased by 0.8% when compared with conventional diesel it is due to it is due to presence of more carbon chains in the blend because of higher percentage of surfactant.

Fig.4.1(a) Comparison of Brake Thermal Efficiency with conventional diesel and blends of biodiesel

Brake Specific Fuel Consumption, The Fig.4.1(b) represents the variation of brake specific fuel consumption with break power for various blends. It is seen that the brake specific fuel consumption is diminishes with rise in brake power. From all the blends M82L15T3 shows the less specific fuel consumption compare to other blends and conventional diesel due to lower calorific value of the blended fuel as compared with diesel and other blends.

Fig..4.1(b) Comparison of BSFC with conventional diesel and blends of biodiesel

Mechanical efficiency, The Fig.4.1(c) represents the variation of Mechanical Efficiency with break power for different blends. From the below graph it is observed that the Mechanical Efficiency is high and also biodiesel blends have less mechanical efficiency due to higher viscosity of the surfactant.

Fig.4.1(c) Comparison of Mechanical Efficiency with conventional diesel and blends of biodiesel

Exhaust gastemperature (EGT), The Fig.4.1(d) shows the exhaust gastemperatures of the CI engine with conventional diesel and different biodiesel blends. The exhaust gas temperatures for the bio diesel blends M85L15, M82L15S3, M82L15T3 and M82L15CTAB3 are very high when compared to conventional diesel which is due to excess availability of oxygen in the combustion chamber and complete combustion.

Fig..4.1(d) Comparison of exhaust gastemperatures

B. Emission characteristics

Hydrocarbon emissions (HC), The Fig.4.2(a) below shows the HC Emissions with conventional diesel and biodiesel blends. It is obvious from the graph that HC emission diesel was 24 ppm where as its value has increased as 26ppm, 27ppm for M85L15, M82L15T3 biodiesel blends and is due to poor atomization and high viscosity of the biodiesel blends.

Fig..4.2(a) Comparison of Hydrocarbons

Carbon monoxide emissions (CO), The variation of CO emissions with BP for different biodiesel blends and diesel is shown in the Fig.4.2(b). The value of CO emissions for M85L15 is 0.19% where as its value has been decreased as 0.17, 0.16 for M82L15S3, M82L15T3 biodiesel blends. And this decrease in value of CO emissions is due to poor atomization and higher carbon chains of surfactant.

Fig.4.2(b) Comparison of Carbon Monoxide

Nitrogen oxide emissions (NO_x), The Fig.4.2(c) examination of NO_x Emissions with conventional diesel and biodiesel blends. The NO_x Emissions are exceptionally high as 405ppm, 417ppm, 422 ppm for biodiesel blends M85L15, M82L15T3, M82L15CTAB3 however for diesel as 375ppm. This increase in NO_x Emissions are because to higher temperatures attained in the engine and also due to poor atomization.

Carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂), The Fig.4.2(d) below shows the CO₂ Emissions with conventional diesel and biodiesel blends. The value of CO₂ Emissions for the biodiesel blends M85L15, M82L15S3, M82L15T3 are 8.2%, 8.5%, 8.7% individually whereas its value for diesel is 8.3%. There is an increase in CO₂ Emissions is because to improper combustion and poor atomization.

Fig.4.2(d) Comparison of Carbon Dioxide

V. CONCLUSION

A diesel engine's performance parameters were tested using diesel fuel and mustard oil/diesel mixtures with various surfactants. We measured the engine's output in relation to its braking thermal efficiency, mechanical efficiency, indicated thermal efficiency, indicated mean effective pressure, and emissions of HC, CO, NO_x, and CO₂. The M82L15T3 mix has a brake thermal efficiency of 17.5%, which is 0.8% higher than regular diesel fuel. More so than with any of the other mixes, the M82L15T3 blend has lower emission levels. Based on the data, it seems that the M82L15T3 mix outperforms all other blends in terms of performance and emissions, suggesting it might be a viable alternative to diesel. The qualities, performance, and emission characteristics of the M82L15T3 blend have been shown to be superior.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Sedaşahin, Hüseyinöğüt Investigation of the Effects of Linseed Oil Biodiesel and Diesel Fuel Blend on Engine Performance and Exhaust Emissions. *International Journal of Automotive Engineering and Technologies* 7(4):149-157
- [2] L.Narsingarao, R.Shiva, T.Suneel. Performance and Emission characteristics of a diesel engine fuelled with biodiesel by using linseed oil. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)* e-ISSN: 2395 -0056 Volume: 04 Issue: 04
- [3] Prof.C.S.Koli, Prof.Ram Bansal, Amit Agrawal, Ashish Agrawal, "Experimental Investigation of Performance of Single Cylinder 4s Diesel Engine Using Dual Vegetable Oil Blended", *Int. Journal of Engineering Research and Applications* ISSN: 2248-9622, Vol.4,
- [4] K. Srinivas, Dr.B.Balu Naik , Dr.K.Kalyani Radha, Impact of Fuel Injection Pressure and Compression Ratio on Performance and Emission Characteristics of VCRCI Engine Fuelled with Palm Kernel Oil-Eucalyptus Oil Blends, 5th International Conference of Materials Processing and Characterization (ICMPC2016),
- [5] G. Prathap Reddy, Dr. K. Hemachandra Reddy experimental study on performance and emissions characteristics of single cylinder diesel engine blended with multi vegetable oils rapeseed and sunflower oils
- [6] Performance study of single cylinder diesel engine with Double biodiesel blends of mustard and neem oils using Alumina coated piston, *IJRAR* July 2018, E-ISSN 2348- 1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138, Volume 5, and Issue 3.
- [7] Kumar, and Reddy, V. K., (2000), "Experimental investigations on the use of vegetable oil fuels in a 4-stroke single cylinder diesel engine", Ph.D Thesis, submitted at JNTU, Anantapur.
- [8] Ramadhas, A.S., Jayaraj, S. and Lakshmi Narayana Rao, K. 2002. Experimental investigation on non-edible vegetable oil operation in diesel engine for improved performance. *National Conference on Advances in Mechanical Engineering, J.N.T.U., Anantapur, India.*
- [9] Gonglun C, Daniel T. An experimental study of stability of oil-water emulsion. *Fuel Process Technol* 2005;86:499-508.
- [10] Texter J. Reactions and synthesis in surfactant systems. Marcel and Dekker; 2001
- [11] Srithar, K. Et al., Experimental investigations on mixing of two biodiesels blended with diesel as alternative fuel for diesel engines. *Journal of King Saud University- Engineering Sciences* (2017) 29, 50-56.
- [12] M.J.Rosen, *Surfactants and Interfacial Phenomena*, Wiley, New York, NY, 2nd edn., 1989.
- [13] D.Myers, *Surfactant Science and Technology*, VCH, New York, 1988.